

Reaction of rice cultivars to bacterial blight, blast, and *Helminthosporium* leaf spot under natural conditions. Punjab, India.

Cross combination	Selections (no.)	Reaction to disease			
		Bacterial blight ^a		Blast ^b at Gurdaspur	<i>Helminthosporium</i> leaf spot ^c at Gurdaspur
		Kapurthala	Gurdaspur		
Basmati 370/Jaya	54	1.7	2.5	2.8	3.5
Norin 18/Hyb 27	52	0.8	2.0	4.7	3.3
Mutants of Basmati 370	33	1.3	2.2	2.1	3.0
Basmati 370/Hamsa	22	1.2	2.2	4.0	3.1
Basmati 370/IR127-80-1-10	5	1.6	2.6	2.4	2.2
IRB/Basmati 370	4	0.7	2.0	3.0	2.5
Phulpattas 72/Mut 65	4	1.7	2.7	2.5	3.5
Basmati 370/IR8	3	1.0	1.7	3.0	2.7
Hyb 27/Mut 65	2	3.5	3.5	2.5	4.5
Mut 52/Basmati 370	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.0
Basmati 370/IR480-5	1	1.0	1.0	3.0	5.0
UPR71-12	1	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
UPR71-21	1	3.0	2.0	2.0	3.0
UPR70/30-4	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
UPR70/30-7	1	2.0	3.0	2.0	3.0
UPR70/30-14	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
UPR70/30-15	1	3.0	3.0	2.0	3.0
UPR70/30-25	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.0
UPR70/30-26	1	0	3.0	3.0	5.0
UPR70/30-39	1	3.0	3.0	2.0	3.0
Jaya	—	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.7
PR106	—	1.3	1.7	2.0	3.0
Palman 579	—	2.0	2.3	1.7	3.0
Basmati 370	—	1.3	2.7	1.7	3.0

^a0 = no infection (immune); 1 = 1–1% of leaf area infected (moderately resistant); 2 = 11–25% (moderately susceptible); 3 = 26–50% (susceptible); 4 = more than 50% infection (highly susceptible).

^bRated only at Gurdaspur. 1 = immune, 2 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 4 = susceptible, 5 = 50% of leaves infected, 6 = 75% of leaves infected, 7 = 100% of leaves infected.

^cRated only at Gurdaspur. 1 = highly resistant, 2 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 4 = moderately susceptible, 5 = susceptible, 6 = very susceptible.

and the cultivar PR106 were moderately resistant to bacterial blight. Palman 579 and Basmati 370 were resistant to blast.

Most of the rices gave resistant to moderately resistant reactions to *Helminthosporium* leaf spot. \mathcal{W}

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Reaction of rice breeding lines to bacterial blight

P. Varadarajan Nair and K. M. Rajan, Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Alleppey, Kerala, India

Bacterial blight of rice incited by *Xanthomonas oryzae* is a serious disease in Kuttanad tract of Kerala, India. Forty-one advanced promising rice cultures developed at the Rice Research Station, Moncompu, were artificially inoculated with a viable and fresh bacterial suspension to study their reactions to bacterial blight. The IRRI leaf clipping method was adapted to the greenhouse for the study. Twelve cultures recorded disease scores below 4: M24-179-1, M24-39-1, M23-57-2-1, M23-17-1-2, M23-33-2-1, M23-57-1-2, M23-83-1-1-2, M23-33-3-1, M23-9-1-1, M23-73-1-1-2, M13-116-1, and M23-16-1-1. \mathcal{W}

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Feeding of brown planthopper on rice varieties labeled with ³²P

P. C. Lippold, J. O. Lee, Y. H. Kim, S. J. Park, J. Ryu, K. H. Chung, M. D. Davis, and K. Steenberg, Crop Improvement Research Center and Institute of Agricultural Science, Office of Rural Development, Suweon 170, and Korean Atomic Energy Research Institute, Seoul, Korea

The importance of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*

has increased in recent years in the Republic of Korea. A 1975 BPH outbreak was especially severe because unusually warm summer temperatures caused a generation advance (BPH do not overwinter in Korea; they migrate annually in late spring and early summer from the Asian mainland).

The use of radioisotopes to complement conventional screening and evaluation of new breeding lines and varieties was investigated in 1976. In

initial trials, three varieties that differed widely in BPH resistance in conventional trials were evaluated by radiotracer methods. The varieties were Yushin, a new high yielding variety; Jinheung, an indigenous japonica; and IR747, a BPH-resistant line.

Six 10-day-old seedlings of each variety were wrapped lightly with a band of absorbent cotton and inserted in 1.27-cm (1/2-inch) holes in a stainless steel plate. The plate was suspended over a